

A Situational Assessment Module for CCAM Applications

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Abstract—The rapid growth of connectivity and automation has led to the rise of Connected Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM), which aims to enhance transportation systems through integrated networks of vehicles, pedestrians, infrastructure, and cloud services. However, increased connectivity also introduces new cyber threats. This study focuses on improving the situational awareness of AI-based systems to detect anomalies, including those caused by cyber-attacks. It proposes a Situational Assessment Module (SAM) for CCAM ecosystems, which uses AI to compare data from vehicle sensors and Roadside Units (RSUs) with internal vehicle messages, detecting anomalies and assessing risk levels. Four AI models are developed to detect specific anomalies, including GNSS loss-spoofing, RSU-vehicle mismatches, lateral and longitudinal motion anomalies. For risk assessment, a rule-based system interprets the severity and probability of anomalies to guide the vehicle’s safe operation.

Index Terms—CCAM, Situational Awareness, AI, Cybersecurity, Risk Assessment, Anomaly Detection, Urban Scenarios.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancements in automotive technology, particularly in Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) and Autonomous Driving (AD), have increased the focus on improving transportation safety, efficiency, and comfort. Intelligent transportation systems have emerged as innovative solutions aimed at enhancing traffic safety and promoting intelligent mobility [1]. However, achieving safety goals relies heavily on situational awareness, which is crucial for autonomous vehicles operating in open environments [2]. The European Commission has emphasized key developments in communication, cybersecurity, sensors, and mobility for urban transportation [3], [4]. The field of AD encompasses a multitude of potential scenarios and sensor modalities, including camera, lidar, and radar [5], but sensor reliability remains a concern due to potential anomalies caused by weather, technical issues, or cyber-attacks [6]. Identifying and classifying these anomalies is essential to distinguish malicious autonomous vehicles from others [7].

There are some researches about risk assessment of autonomous vehicles. However these works mainly focus on assessment of risk related to collision [8]–[10]. The Situational Assessment Module (SAM) plays a key role in detecting

anomalies, misuse, and malfunctions by analyzing data from the environment, onboard sensors, and the vehicle’s trajectory. The module uses AI to detect anomalies and it assess risks in real-time, focusing on tasks related to autonomous vehicle, such as perception, localization, and vehicle movements. SAM actively participates in the vehicle’s safety system, determining risk levels based on detected anomalies and influencing the vehicle’s safe operation mode accordingly. This paper explores SAM’s architecture, its AI models for anomaly detection, and its contributions to the safety and efficiency of autonomous vehicles, built on the framework of the EU-SELFY project to enhance the security and resilience of the Connected Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) environment.

II. SITUATIONAL ASSESSMENT MODULE IN THE SELFY PROJECT

The SELFY project, funded by the Horizon Europe program, focuses on developing tools to enhance the resilience of the CCAM ecosystem against cyber-attacks and hazards. Launched in 2022, the three-year project aims to create a toolbox of modules, each contributing to SELFY’s larger goals. The Situational Awareness and Collaborative Perception (SACP) Macro Tool provides comprehensive environmental understanding through vehicle and Roadside Unit (RSU) data. The Cooperative Resilience and Healing System (CRHS) Macro Tool activates self-protective measures when vulnerabilities are detected. The Trust Data Management System (TDMS) ensures secure data management within the CCAM ecosystem.

The proposed architectural framework is depicted in “Fig. 1”. SAM is integrated between SACP and CRHS, utilizing enhanced perception from SACP and sending its outputs to CHRS, enabling Safety Operational Tools [11] to take action for vehicle safety. These processes can occur locally or collaboratively to support global CCAM-level decision-making.

III. SITUATIONAL ASSESSMENT MODULE

The SAM, shown in “Fig. 2” processes data from the Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) network, the ego vehicle network, and the environment model. This is done utilising

Fig. 1. Situational Assessment Module in the SELFY project.

a number of AI models in order to identify unusual circumstances and to determine the risk status of the vehicle. Four distinct AI models were developed for this anomaly identification. In order to ascertain these anomalies, a variety of data and scenarios were employed to achieve the thorough and realistic results.

The initial model is that of GNSS loss-spoofing detection, which employs a distance estimation methodology to discern instances wherein vehicles experience a loss of GNSS data or instances where GNSS data has been manipulated. The second model is RSU-Vehicle Mismatch detection, whereby discrepancies between the data obtained from vehicle perception and that obtained from RSU perception indicate the potential for an issue to have occurred. The third model is longitudinal motion anomaly detection, which involves the identification of unexpected changes in acceleration or deceleration. The last model is lateral motion anomaly detection, which monitors the vehicle’s lane position and trajectory to detect issues such as lane departure or zigzagging.

After detection of anomalies the frequency, probability, and severity of anomalies are calculated. Subsequently, a risk score is assigned on the basis of a rule-based decision table that utilises the calculated values. The risk score serves to inform the subsequent module of the appropriate action for the safe operation of the system.

Fig. 2. Situational Assessment Module in the SELFY project.

IV. CONCLUSION

The SELFY project aims to become the leading European provider of a comprehensive toolbox for managing the security and resilience of the CCAM ecosystem, addressing threats like cyber-attacks. The SELFY toolbox includes three key macro-tools: SACP, CRHS, and TDMS. This article presents SAM, an

AI-based tool that enhances situational awareness by detecting and evaluating anomalies caused by cyber-attacks. SAM uses AI to process environmental data, detect anomalies, and assess risks to ensure safe vehicle operation.

The results were obtained by testing SAM’s collaborative perception during real driving and simulated scenarios using the CARLA environment. Moving forward, the SELFY project will continue integrating and validating the toolbox in real-world environments, aiming to provide a comprehensive security solution for stakeholders like OEMs, suppliers, and transportation providers. SAM’s capabilities will expand to detect more types of anomalies and identify specific cyber-attacks, further strengthening its resilience.

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